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THE IMPACT OF GLOBALISATION ON LANGUAGE AS AN INTEGRAL PART OF UKRAINIAN SOCIETY CULTURE

Nataliia Sarnovska^{1a}, Maryna Antonivska^{2a}

¹Lecturer,

ORCID: 0000-0001-7278-5183, e-mail: nat_sarnovskaya@ukr.net,

²Lecturer,

ORCID: 0000-0002-4451-3735, e-mail: antonivska_maryna@ukr.net,

^aKyiv National University of Culture and Arts,

36, Ye. Konovaltsia St., Kyiv, 01133, Ukraine

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Abstract

The purpose of the article is to consider the features and forms of influence of globalisation as an integral part of the culture of society, the consequences of this process on the languages of other nations, given the global spread of English; determine the positive and negative aspects of the impact of globalisation on the modern Ukrainian language; demonstrate the need for coexistence of both languages (Ukrainian, English), given the preservation of linguistic identity against the excessive penetration of the English adoptions. Research methodology. The research methods include study, analysis, and generalisation to demonstrate the influence of globalisation and its implications for languages, particularly Ukrainian, in the modern world. Scientific novelty. The article considers the matter of language in the context of globalisation under current trends: the transformation of English into a single global language of international communication and the process of mass extinction of languages. The work studies the language situation in European and post-Soviet countries and analyses the influence of English on the modern Ukrainian language. Conclusions. Post-industrialism has led humanity to enter the era of globalisation. This concept is based on the principle of unification. Integration between countries and their cultures has increased. The dialogue of cultures is taking place at this stage against the background of globalisation. As a result, we conclude that any process in the language (Ukrainian, English, etc.) cannot be considered in isolation but only in the context of all the factors that determine this process. All these processes have both positive and negative effects on existing languages. Integration into the world community without multilingualism is impossible today because the modern world is already multilingual. Given that life is divided into spheres — there is the language of business, technology, science and everyday language of everyday communication, the

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language of literature and art. Therefore, it is necessary to understand, in Ukraine, it requires both languages' proficiency (in Ukrainian and English).

■ **Keywords:** globalization; culture; language; intercultural communication; national identity

■ Introduction

Globalisation has increased the intensity of cultural exchanges, essentially expanding the circle of those who make a constant process of transition from one cultural world to another. It has made the borders for talents transparent, removed restrictions on the movement of outstanding performers, conductors, artists, directors from country to country, many of whom now spend much more time abroad than at home. The results of the creativity of geniuses in the context of globalisation cease to be the property of this or that nation but become the property of all mankind.

Globalisation has legitimised the existence of a certain cultural standard, according to which a person of the information society must master foreign languages, communicate with representatives of other countries and be acquainted with their culture, use a personal computer, understand various directions of art, literature, philosophy, science, etc.

The process of globalisation is currently being discussed in all branches of modern science: sociology, political science, computer science, linguistics and, of course, cultural studies.

An analysis of the situation that has developed in language and culture under the influence of modern globalisation processes reflects the general dual nature of globalisation. The contradictory, dual nature of globalisation is manifested when considering it in the system of cultural coordinates. On the one hand, globalisation contributes to the acceleration of "sociodynamics of culture" (Moles, 2008). Under its influence, the rates of production, distribution and consumption of cultural values are sharply increasing. The time of the culture conversion cycle is sharply reduced, which leads to a growth of information received by the individual, the enlargement of his horizons, and an increase in the intellectual level. Thanks to new information technologies, a person of a global society got the opportunity to know a number of artefacts that were unreachable to people of an industrial and post-industrial society due to the lack of a significant part of them the chance to make sightseeing trips to different countries, travel around the world, use the services provided by the famous repositories of cultural values where a significant part of the world cultural heritage is concentrated. Virtual museums, libraries, art galleries and concert halls that exist in the "world information web" provide an opportunity to get acquainted with everything that was created by the genius of this or that artist, architect, composer, regardless of where these or those masterpieces: in Paris, London, Brussels or Washington. The topic of globalisation has remained relevant for the last decades. The world is changing, and society, its values and culture are changing along with it. A large number of domestic scientists and their colleagues abroad study this issue, considering globalisation and its impact from various angles in various aspects of the existence of society, taking into account the positive and negative aspects of this influence.

In our work, we relied on the studies of T. Vozniak (1998), L. Zemlyanova (1999), V. Sheiko (2001, 2009), B. Azhniuk (2001, 2021), as well as the works of J. Bartelson (2000), J. Meyer (2000), A. Moles (2008), S. P. Huntington (2006), A. Kearney (2016), Rehnuma Sazzad (2020). As a scientific term, globalisation is used primarily in research related to real-world dynamics.

In the dictionary of terms and concepts of modern mass media, L. Zemlyanova (1999) defines globalisation as the spread of information materials, communications, tools and systems on a transnational scale worldwide. S. Denysova (2003) proposes to call words, phrases, expressions related to these processes of globalisation, globalism.

In the paper "The interaction of globalisation and culture in the modern world" by Sadykova R. et al. (2014), it is emphasised that "globalisation contributes to the exchange of cultural values".

The well-known philosopher A. Panarin believes that globalisation "is defined as a process of weakening traditional territorial, socio-cultural and state-political barriers that once isolated peoples from each other, but at the same time protected them from disordered external influences, and the formation of a new, unprotected system of international interaction and interdependence" (Panarin, 2000).

Globalisation has sharply exacerbated the problem of national cultural identity, which today has become one of the most important problems, which worries not only cultural experts but also politicians, public scientists and religious figures, linguists, progressive-minded representatives of the natural sciences.

■ **Purpose of the Article**

The purpose of the article is to consider the features and forms of influence of globalisation as an integral part of the culture of society, the consequences of this process on the languages of other nations, given the global spread of English. Note the positive and negative aspects of the impact of globalisation on the modern Ukrainian language.

■ **Main Research Material**

Today, to varying degrees, all countries of the world are covered by the process of globalisation. Globalisation is an objective process of formation, organisation, functioning and development of a fundamentally new world, a global system based on the relationship used in all spheres of the international community. The concept of "globalisation" is multifaceted. More broadly, it is the outgrowth of national and regional problems into the global and forming a new economic, social and natural-biological environment. Specific areas of globalisation are moral and ethical values and the current language situation.

Globalisation refers to the expansion and deepening of social ties and institutions in space and time in such a way that, on the one hand, the daily activities of people are increasingly influenced by events taking place in other parts of the globe, on the other hand, the actions of local communities can have important global implications.

Initially, the development of relationships between peoples and countries proceeded in the form of the expansion of Europe, and then the West as a whole, so

globalisation meant, in essence, European, Western globalisation. Now the processes of regionalisation and globalisation have covered the entire globe. It should be noted that globalisation is also the most important category of the new problem area. However, its linguistic significance has been recognised by scientists relatively recently.

Globalisation also has a linguistic aspect. It is unthinkable without finding a common language in the literal and figurative sense. The language of a people is its historical memory. It is an integral part of the culture and its tool; it is the reality of our spirit, the face of culture; it expresses in naked form the specific features of the national mentality. The language is able to reflect the cultural and national mentality of its speakers. Against the background of evolving globalisation processes in the perspective of the cultural approach, culture is seen as the dominant of social life, which transforms society and the environment and becomes a factor in life and a source of innovation. Such a view of culture leads to the emergence in the Cultural Studies of a new worldview paradigm — cultural centrism, which insists on assessing the world from the standpoint of culture. Therefore, it is not surprising that in the perspective of interdisciplinary research related to globalisation, attention is focused on changes in culture, which, in turn, is closely linked to changes in language.

Globalisation and related integration processes with the help of mass media, the Internet, the development of new modes of transport destroy the former isolation of ethnic communities, erase the territorial and cultural boundaries of ethnic identity. To provide the most effective conditions for communication, dialogue

of cultures, these processes often exclude the principle of diversity, contributing to the unification of cultural standards. The mechanisms of continuity of generations and the organisation of the cultural space of ethnic groups that have been formed for centuries are being destroyed, leading to a crisis of ethnocultural identity.

At the beginning of the third millennium, a person found himself on the “borders” of many social and cultural worlds, the contours of which are increasingly blurred due to the globalisation of the cultural space, high communication, pluralisation of languages and lifestyles. The problem of crisis or loss of identity is being discussed more and more often.

The leading features and features of the ethnic picture of the world are fixed primarily in the language as a mechanism for reproducing the defining features of ethnic culture, thanks to which the historical memory of the people is preserved, the ethnocultural experience of generations is transmitted, the norms of behaviour expressed in the language and the peculiarities of the organisation of the way of life are fixed. Language is the main carrier and powerful relay of ethno-social ideas. The formation of the lexical composition and semantic content of the communicative space of ethnic groups took place in the process of historical and cultural development. These features play a very important role in maintaining the integrity of society and socio-cultural continuity. Any language, accumulating the experience of people's lives in all its fullness and diversity, is its real consciousness. Each new generation, each representative of a particular ethnic group, mastering the language, is included in a historically defined system of social relations, joins the collective experience, collective knowledge about the environment reality, generally accepted norms of be-

haviour, socio-cultural values. The language captures the cognitive experience of the people, their moral, ethical, socio-aesthetic, artistic and educational ideals.

The language keeps the history of the civilisational development of the people. It reflects the national character, norms of relations accepted and preserved from generation to generation with other people and standards of social behaviour, relations with other peoples. The language has absorbed the peculiarities of the attitude of the ethnos to the surrounding reality, its perception in the system of values and assessments, and the motivation of behaviour. Language is not only a sign system, it is also a tool, in its way coordinating the social development of a person who is a native speaker of a given language.

The socio-cultural experience of many generations, fixed and systematised in the language, in its way forms the representation of a person about the world around him. Each language carries out the designation of objects and phenomena of the surrounding reality in different ways since the building material of thought is a specific language with its own unique national identity is the building material of thought. Thus, firstly, in the new civilisational conditions, determined by the processes of globalisation and new information and communication technologies, the problem of ethnocultural identity has indicated the need to develop a new approach to considering the role of language as a socio-cultural mechanism of ethno-cultural continuity. "Every society elaborates codes of communication that are thought of essential for the transmission of information and social and intercultural encounters — just think of oral, written, non-verbal and visual communication" (Ysmailova et al., 2020, p. 483).

A foreign language has historically been the most important subject of general education. But its educative and developing reserves have not yet been studied. The ideas about it boil down to the fact that the study of a foreign language lays the foundations for foreign language speech activity. Language is an additional means of broadening one's horizons. Together with the study of the native language, a foreign language helps to understand the universal ways of verbal communication better, contributes to the education of the moral qualities of the individual

One of the most common foreign languages is English. English has an important place in people's lives in today's world. It was just a foreign language more recently, but now it is an international language. Many European states have more than a century of experience in international communication through English. More and more, we are faced with a situation where modern information technologies are based entirely on the material of the English language, at international scientific conferences reports are read and published mainly in English, and international negotiations are conducted not through an interpreter but in English on both sides.

Borrowing processes go on with varying degrees of intensity throughout the entire period of language development. Still, there are times when the influx of foreign words and phrases is incredibly intense. For the modern Ukrainian language, the 90s years of the 20th century became such a period. The collapse of the Soviet Union meant the destruction of most of the barriers that stood in the way of communication between Ukraine and the Western world. Ukrainian society has become more open and predisposed to contact other countries. Business, scientific, trade and cultural ties have become more active; overseas tourism flourished; joint ventures emerged

and began to operate successfully. A natural consequence of this was the entry into the Russian language of a significant number of anglicisms.

Many other reasons contribute to the massive and relatively easy penetration of foreign neologisms into the Ukrainian language. Reasons of a socio-psychological nature occupy an important place among them: many native speakers of the Ukrainian language consider a foreign word more prestigious than the corresponding native one. A change in political, economic, and ideological guidelines has led to a pronounced "Americanization" in Ukraine, when not only technical innovations are attractive, but also living standards, behaviour and communication, and tastes. There is an active displacement of Ukrainian words by English borrowings.

The adoption process is also intensified due to a foreign word's greater economy and rationality than the original or tracing descriptive expression. So, a speechwriter is a speechwriter for an official, casting is the selection of candidates for participation in a program, filming a film, a remake is an updated version of an old piece of music.

Due to the adoption of a significant number of words with a similar morphological structure, word-formation means are also borrowed, for example, semi-free morphemes time-, show-, -gate, -maker, etc.

Few anglicisms these days are taken away from common Ukrainian words: exclusive, briefing, shaping, training, roaming, tuning, show, cooler, hit, clip, DJ, thriller, service, mixer, player, toaster, marketing, shop, dealer, provider, promoter, sponsor, grant, applicant, speaker, grill, chips, hot dog, cheeseburger, timer, weekend, image, nonsense, electorate, establishment, inauguration, impeachment, supermarket, price list, play-maker, business lady, top model, public relations, mass media, press release, jackpot, permanent, and so on.

The Ukrainian language turned out to be very receptive to mastering the English designations that came with specific artefacts and concepts of the new world. The Ukrainian language actively functions in the youth environment and youth discourse, especially actively absorbing and absorbing new language forms and meanings of anglicisms.

The new conditions for the functioning of the Ukrainian language began to separate generations more clearly. The older generation is increasingly moving away from the youth, who easily and naturally immerse themselves in the world of the Internet and freely use its various services.

■ Conclusions

The analysis of the existence and development of languages in the context of globalisation allows the authors to draw the following conclusions. The global process of globalisation initiates the emergence and rapid spread of television, computers and the Internet, global trade liberalisation, and expanding international organisations' scope. This process is objectively valid and can be both positive and negative aspects. Kofi Annan once said, "It has been said that arguing against globalisation is like arguing against the laws of gravity" (Crossette, 2000).

The more globalisation processes penetrate national cultures, the more people strive to protect their internal components, such as language, religion, traditions, culture. That is, in the era of global restructuring, the most acute problems are national

identity, which is directly related to the desire of peoples for self-determination and identity in the modern world, with the desire to defend and preserve their identity. Despite the intensification of the globalisation process, in Ukraine, at the same time, there is an increasing interest in national traditions and the revival of the native language.

From a practical point of view, there are two approaches for Ukraine — monolingual and multilingual. Integration into the world community without multilingualism is impossible today because the modern world is already multilingual. Given that life is divided into spheres — there is the language of business, technology, science and everyday language of everyday communication, the language of literature and art. Therefore, it is necessary to understand that the normal situation in Ukraine is the need to speak both languages (meaning Ukrainian and English), especially for future professionals, the need for coexistence of both languages, given the preservation of linguistic identity from excessive penetration of English borrowings.

There is a growing list of people actively learning English, computer technologies that allow them to realise themselves as a person in modern globalised society. However, traditional values, their historical past and religious worldviews still actively influence the formation of deep layers of identity. The manifestation of a sense of national pride while respecting other peoples, preserving one's spiritual values and cultural traditions, and promoting the world should become the basis of cultural identification in the modern world.

References

- Azhniuk, B. (2001). Movni zminy na tli dekolonizatsii ta hlobalizatsii [Language Changes Against the Background of Decolonization and Globalization]. *Movoznavstvo*, 3, 48–54 [in Ukrainian].
- Azhniuk, B. (2021). Movna polityka: natsionalna identychnist i yevropeiski tsinnosti [Modern Politics: National Identity and European Values]. *Bulletin of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine*, 6, 89–93 [in Ukrainian].
- Bartelson, J. (2000). Three Concept of Globalization. *International Sociology*, 15(2), 180–196 [in English].
- Crossette, B. (2000, September 7). Globalisation Tops 3-Day U.N. Agenda For World Leaders. *The New York Times*, 3. <https://www.nytimes.com/2000/09/07/world/globalization-tops-3day-un-agenda-for-world-leaders.html> [in English].
- Denysova, S. (2003). Hlobalizmy u zasobah masovoi infotmatsii [Globalisms in the Media]. *Scientific Notes of Vinnytsia Mykhailo Kotsiubynskyi State Pedagogical University. Series: Philology (Linguistics)*, 6, 390–395 [in Ukrainian].
- Huntington, S. P. (2006). *Protystoiannia tsyvilizatsii ta zmina svitivoho poriadku. [Confrontation of Civilisations and Change of World Order]*. Calvary [in Ukrainian].
- Kearney, A. (2016). *Exploring the Impact of Globalisation on Linguistic Culture*. Honors Theses. 2725. https://scholarworks.wmich.edu/honors_theses/2725 [in English].
- Meyer, J. W. (2000). Globalisation. Sources and Effects on National States and Societies. *International Sociology*, 15(2), 233–248 [in English].
- Moles, A. (2008). *Sotsiodinamika kultury [Sociodynamics of Culture]* (3rd ed.). Lki Izdatel'stvo [in Russian].

- Panarin, A. (2000). *Politologiya [Political science]*. Gardarika [in Russian].
- Sadykova, R., Myrzabekov, M., Myrzabekova, R., & Moldakhmetkyzy, A. (2014). The Interaction of Globalization and Culture in the Modern World. *Procedia — Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 122, 8–12. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.01.1294> [in English].
- Sazzad, R. (2020, June 3). The Effects of Globalisation on Languages and Cultural Diversity. *Culture, Equal Rights, Politics & Foreign Affairs*. <https://impakter.com/effects-of-globalisation-on-languages-and-cultural-diversity/> [in English].
- Sheiko, V. (2001). *Kultura. Tsyvilizatsiia. Hlobalizatsiia (kinets XIX – pochatok XXI stolittia) [Culture. Civilisation. Globalisation (the End of the 19th Century – the Beginning of the 21st Century)]* [Monograph] (Vol. 2). Osnova [in Ukrainian].
- Sheiko, V. (2009). Kultura ta hlobalizatsiia; komparatyvistskyi analiz [Culture and Globalization: a Comparative Analysis]. *The Culturology Ideas*, 1, 73–79 [in Ukrainian].
- Vozniak, T. (1998). *Teksty ta pereklady [Texts and Translations]*. Folio [in Ukrainian].
- Ysmailova, R., Kochkonbayeva, S., Zhakaeva, G., Salieva, D., Dyikanbayeva, R., Alymbayeva, A., Madmarova, Z., Adylbekova, B., & Dzheenbaeva, K. (2020) Integration of National Languages through a Global Communication System: Culture Reflection. *Open Journal of Philosophy*, 10, 482–493. <https://doi.org/10.4236/ojpp.2020.104034> [in English].
- Zemlyanova, L. (1999). *Zarubezhnaya kommunikativistika v preddverii informatsionnogo obshchestva [Foreign Communication Studies on the eve of the Information Society]: Explanatory dictionary of terms and concepts*. Moscow University Publishing House [in Russian].

■ ВПЛИВ ГЛОБАЛІЗАЦІЇ НА МОВУ ЯК НЕВІД'ЄМНУ ЧАСТИНУ КУЛЬТУРИ УКРАЇНСЬКОГО СУСПІЛЬСТВА

■ Сарновська Наталія Іванівна^{1а}, Антонівська Марина Олександрівна^{2а}

■ ¹Викладач,

ORCID: 0000-0001-7278-5183, e-mail: nat_sarnovskaya@ukr.net,

■ ²Викладач,

ORCID: 0000-0002-4451-3735, e-mail: antonivska_maryna@ukr.net,

^аКиївський національний університет культури і мистецтва,

Київ, Україна

■ Анотація

Мета статті — розглянути особливості та форми впливу глобалізації як невід'ємної частини культури суспільства, наслідки цього процесу на мови інших народів з огляду на глобальне поширення англійської мови; визначити позитивні та негативні сторони впливу глобалізації на сучасну українську мову; продемонструвати необхідність співіснування обох мов (української, англійської), враховуючи збереження мовної ідентичності від надмірного проникнення англомовних запозичень. Методологія охоплює дослідження, аналіз та узагальнення з метою продемонструвати вплив глобалізації та

її наслідки для мов, зокрема української, у сучасному світі. Наукова новизна. У статті розглянуто мовне питання в контексті глобалізації за сучасних тенденцій: перетворення англійської мови в єдину глобальну мову міжнародного спілкування та процесу масового вимирання мов; досліджено мовну ситуацію в країнах Європи та пострадянського простору; проаналізовано вплив англійської мови на сучасну українську мову. Висновки. Постіндустріалізм став причиною входження людства в епоху глобалізації. Ця концепція заснована на принципі уніфікації. Зросла інтеграція між країнами та культурами. На цьому етапі діалог культур відбувається на тлі глобалізації. Отже, будь-який процес у мові (українській, англійській тощо) не можна розглядати ізольовано, а лише в контексті всіх чинників, що визначають його. Усі ці процеси мають як позитивний, так і негативний вплив на існуючі мови. Інтеграція у світову спільноту без багатомовності сьогодні неможлива, оскільки сучасний світ уже багатомовний. З огляду на те, що життя поділено на сфери — є мова бізнесу, техніки, науки й побутова мова повсякденного спілкування, мова літератури та мистецтва. Тому слід розуміти, що в Україні є необхідність володіння обома мовами (йдеться про українську та англійську) на належному рівні.

■ **Ключові слова:** глобалізація; культура; мова; міжкультурна комунікація; національна ідентичність

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